

Review of Flood & Carson (2nd edition)

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Designing involves changing humans' futures. It is a complex activity that requires addressing complex problems spanning different social, natural, technical and infomatic systems and different domains.

Using many case studies and examples, Flood and Carson skillfully overview key approaches to addressing problems involving complexity from the field of systems science: the centre of research and knowledge in addressing and resolving complex systems problems.

The book is multi-layered, with three themes: Addressing complexity (Chapters 1-11), using different systems models in the technical world and natural sciences (Chapters 3-10), and addressing problems in systems that additionally include complexity from human behaviour, learning and cognition (Chapters 5-7).

The second edition of this book is a classic text that benefits by feedback on the first edition. It is aimed at the middle ground in a field that ranges from difficult philosophical issues, through systemic problem-solving approaches, to difficult mathematical procedures and concepts.

It is likely to be useful in raising the quality of output of designers in most domains and worthy of a place on most designers' bookshelves.